

A STUDY OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN COMMUNICATIVE BEHAVIOUR AND TEACHING COMPETENCY OF HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS IN CUDDALORE DISTRICT

Dr. S. Kalaivani* & S. Soniya**

* Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Annamalai University,
Chidambaram, Tamilnadu

** M.Ed Scholar, Department of Education, Annamalai University, Chidambaram, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Dr. S. Kalaivani & S. Soniya, "A Study of the Relationship between Communicative Behaviour and Teaching Competency of High School Teachers in Cuddalore District", International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education, Volume 2, Issue 2, Page Number 407-408, 2017.

Copy Right: © IJCRME, 2017 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

The present study aims to study the relationship between communicative behavior and teaching competency of high school teachers in Cuddalore district. Simple random sampling technique has been used in the selection of the various schools in Cuddalore District. To measure communication behavior, the investigator has used "Rajan communication behavior inventory" and the investigator has also used "Amaladoss teaching competency inventory" for teaching competency. Result shows that there is a positive relationship between communication behavior and teaching competency.

Introduction:

Communication as an academic discipline relates to all the ways we communicate, so it embraces a large body of study and knowledge. The communication discipline includes both verbal and nonverbal messages. A body of scholarship all about communication is presented and explained in textbooks, electronic publications, and academic journals. In the journals, researchers report the results of studies that are the basis for an ever-expanding understanding of how we all communicate. Communication happens at many levels (even for one single action), in many different ways, and for most beings, as well as certain machines. Several, if not all, fields of study dedicate a portion of attention to communication, so when speaking about communication it is very important to be sure about what aspects of communication one is speaking about. Definitions of communication range widely, some recognizing that animals can communicate with each other as well as human beings, and some are more narrow, only including human beings within the parameters of human symbolic interaction.

Teaching Competencies:

David G. Rayns, (1969) described the two types of teaching competencies, "Teaching is complex and many-sided, demanding a variety of human traits and abilities. These may be grouped in to two major categories—first, those involving the teacher's mental abilities and skills, his understandings of psychological and educational principles and his knowledge of general and specific subject-matter to be taught and second, those qualities stemming from the teacher's personality, his interests, attitudes and beliefs, his behavior in working relationships with pupils and other individuals and the like".

Objectives:

- To find out the relationship between communicative behavior and teaching competency of high school teachers.

Hypothesis:

- There is no significant relationship between communicative behaviour and teaching competency of high school teachers

Sample of the Study:

- The present study was conducted on a representative sample of 300 high school teachers in Cuddalore district.

Tools Used:

- The investigator has used "Rajan communication behaviour inventory". It is a self-appraised inventory developed by Dr. Sathiyagiri rajan. (1981)
- The investigator has used "Amaladoss teaching competency inventory". It is a self-rating type by the teachers. It was developed by Dr. Fr. Amaladoss Xavier S.J. (1986)

Description of the Tool Communicative Behaviour:

- This inventory tries to find out the communicative behaviour of the teachers. There are 25 items and take items are divided into some for each dimensions of the communicative behaviour.
- It is a self-reporting five points scale viz. A-Almost always, B-Often, C-Uncertain, D-Sometimes, E-Rarely.

Description of the Tool Teaching Competency:

There are 48 items and take items are divided into some for each dimensions of the teaching competency. The number of statements to be answered with five options namely A-Always, B-Regularly, C-Occasionally, D-Rarely and E-Never are given below. The scale is of self-rating type by the teachers.

Scoring Procedure:

Of the five options available for each item the respondent has to a tick mark against an item. If the respondent put a tick mark on always, then a score of '5' is given, for regularly '4', for occasionally '3', for rarely '2', and for never '1', is to be awarded.

Establishing Validity of the Inventory:

The investigator has established content validity of the tool. The tool has been given to the experts in high school, Cuddalore District. All the experts fully agree with the items given in the inventory. Thus the content validity of the tool has been established.

Establishing Reliability of the Inventory:

The investigator has established test, re-test reliability. The inventory has been administered to 28 teacher in high school teachers. The same inventory has been given to the same 28 teachers in the same school on after one week. Their responses are scored and two sets of scores are obtained. The correlation between these two sets of scores are found by using product moment correlation. It is found to be which is satisfactory.

Distribution of the Sample:

300 high school teachers were selected from Rural and Urban areas of schools in Cuddalore district.

Administration of the Research Tools:

Correlation of Communicative Behaviour and Teaching Competency:

Hypothesis:

There is no significant relationship between communicative behaviour and teaching competency of high school teachers.

Relationship between Communicative Behaviour and Teaching Competency of High School Teachers:

Variables	Numbers	Correlation coefficient (r) value	Level of significance
Communicative behaviour and Teaching competency	300	0.39	Significant

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 'r' value is 0.39 which is greater than the table value at 5% level of significance. Hence null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, the result is that, there is significant relationship between communicative behaviour and teaching competency of high school teachers.

Conclusion:

There is a positive relationship between neurotic communicative behaviour and teaching competency and there is no significant relationship between extrovert communicative behaviour and teaching competency.

References:

1. Al-Najjar, Rana Abdel-Rahman (2012). "An Evaluation of Pronunciation. Teaching Content of "English for Palestine 10" and Related Teachers' Competency Level in Light of Current Instructional Perspectives". Online Submission, Master's Thesis, The Islamic University of Gaza.
2. Bamber, John; Crowther, Jim (2012). "Speaking Habermas to Gramsci: Implications for the Vocational Preparation of Community Educators". Studies in Philosophy and Education, v31 n2 p183-197.
3. Brok, Perry; van Eerde, Dolly; Hajer, Maaïke (2010). "Classroom Interaction Studies as a Source for Teacher Competencies: The Use of Case Studies with Multiple Instruments for Studying Teacher Competencies in Multicultural Classes". Teachers and Teaching: Theory and Practice, v16 n6 p717-733.
4. Stephenson, Jennifer; Dowrick, Margaret (2005). "Parents' Perspectives on the Communication Skills of Their Children with Severe Disabilities". Journal of Intellectual and Developmental Disability, v30 n2 p75-85